

SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTS FOR MECHANICAL PROPERTIES DOMINATING THE PRESS MOLDING USING CFRTP PREFORMS

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Abstract

- In the press molding, draping ability can be improved by preforming, and preforming without defects is required for making high quality products.
- The present paper examined the pull-out property and shear property of CFRTP preforms, which dominate press molding, by experiments, and made simulation models for CFRTP preforming.

Introduction

- High production rates are required to apply CFRP to automotive industry.
 - Press molding using CFRTP
- In the press molding, draping ability can be improved by preforming, and preforming without defects is required for making high quality products.
 - Optimization of the geometrical and constraint conditions

LEXUS LC [1]

For preforming simulations . . .

- Pull-out and shear properties were measured by experiments.
- Simulation models were made and assessed their predictive capabilities.

Materials

- Tape materials: CF/PA 6

Prepreg

The thermoplastic resin film was fully laminated to the carbon fibers.

Semipreg

The thermoplastic resin film was not fully laminated to the carbon fibers.

- Configuration: AP-PLY

Through-the-thickness reinforcements

Automated fiber placement process

	Carbon fiber	Matrix	V _f [%]	Nominal thickness [μm]	Width [mm]
Prepreg	TR50S	PA6	53.4	43	10
Semipreg	TR50S	PA6	37	64	10

[1] <https://lexus.jp/models/lc/gallery/>

[2] S.P. Haanappel, R.H.W. ten Thije, U. Sachs, B. Rietman, R. Akkerman, Composites: Part A 56 (2014) 80–92

Experimental method and results

Pull-out experiments

Tool-ply friction and ply-ply friction were measured.

- A normal load was applied by tightening a screw.
- Fixing horizontal tapes, vertical tapes were pulled out.
- The thermostat temperature was set to 423 K.

→ Friction coefficients were obtained, and there was no clear difference confirmed between the results of two materials.

Shear experiments

Picture-frame tests were carried out.

- The initial contact area of two tapes was 1,600 mm².
- Bundle edges were pinned and free to rotate.
- The specimen was positioned between two aluminum plates which were separated by about 0.32 mm.
- The thermostat temperature was set to 423 K.

→ The shear stiffness increased with increasing shear angle.

Simulation method and results

Pull-out simulations

Fixing horizontal tapes, vertical tapes were pulled-out.

- The configuration of pull-out specimens was reproduced.
- Step1: Two rigid plates D and E were displaced against each other.
- Step2: The upper rigid plate A was displaced upwards with vertical tapes.

→ The present model could reproduce the frictional pull-out of the tapes in the specimen.

Shear simulations

Fixing horizontal tapes, vertical tapes were rotated.

- Boundary conditions were different from the picture-frame test
- Step1: Two rigid plates H and I were displaced against each other.
- Step2: The upper and lower rigid plates F and G were rotated with vertical tapes.

→ The shear stiffness was increased with increasing shear angle, as in picture-frame tests.

Conclusion

- In pull-out tests, friction coefficients between tapes were measured. In picture-frame tests, the shear stiffness increased with increasing shear angle.
- In pull-out simulations, the magnitude of the steady pull-out load was similar to that in the tests. In shear simulations, the shear stiffness increased with increasing shear angle, as in picture-frame tests.